

Grant Agreement Number: 101129658

Project Acronym: SPATRA

Project title: SPACE-BASED APPLICATIONS FOR TRANSPORT MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

Project acronym:	SPATRA
Starting date:	01.01.2024
Duration (in months):	24
Call (part) identifier:	HORIZON-EUSPA-2022-SPACE
Grant agreement no:	101129658
Grant Amendments:	-
Due date of deliverable:	31-03-2024
Actual submission date:	29-04-2024
Coordinator:	Danijela Ristic-Durrant, Senior R&T Project Manager
Lead Beneficiary:	OHB-DS
Version:	01
Type:	R (Report)
Sensitivity or Dissemination level¹:	PU (Public)
Taxonomy/keywords:	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and EUSPA under grant agreement 101129658.

¹ PU: Public; CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including Commission Services)

Document History

Date	Name	Affiliation	Position/Project Role	Action/ Short Description
01/03/2024	Vladimir Radomirović	Zentrix Lab (ZENRS)	WP Leader	Author. Initial content and structure
31/03/2024	Vladimir Radomirović, Vladimir Urošević, Jelena Vasić	Zentrix Lab (ZENRS)	WP Leader	Detailed content and completion of all sections
05/04/2024	Larysa Istomina, Danijela Ristic-Durrant	OHB-DS	Project Coordinator	Peer-reviewed
11/04/2024	Nenad Gligoric	Zentrix Lab OU (ZENE)	Task participant	Editorial changes
15/04/2024	Larysa Istomina	OHB-DS	Scientific & Technical Coordinator	Editorial changes
15/04/2024	Danijela Ristic-Durrant	OHB-DS	Project Coordinator	Approved for distribution
19/04/2024	Danijela Ristic-Durrant, Larysa Istomina	OHB-DS	Project Coordinator	Updated the document according to the expert review
29/04/2024	Danijela Ristic-Durrant	OHB-DS	Project Coordinator	Finalisation for submission upon expert reviewer approval.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority EUSPA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS, ACRONYMS AND DEFINITIONS	5
LIST OF FIGURES.....	6
LIST OF TABLES.....	7
1 INTRODUCTION.....	8
2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES	10
2.1 Relationship of D5.1 to Work Packages, Tasks and Milestones	10
3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH AND TARGETS IDENTIFICATION	11
3.1 Stakeholder Engagement and Systematisation	12
3.1.1 SPATRA Stakeholders Mapping and Segmentation	13
3.1.2 SPATRA Focus Groups.....	16
4 SPATRA DISSEMINATION STRATEGY AND PLAN.....	17
4.1 Dissemination Channels and Tools (Digital, Printed and Events)	18
5 SPATRA COMMUNICATION STRATEGY AND PLAN.....	22
5.1 Established SPATRA Communication Tools and Channels	22
5.1.1 Logo and Visual Identity	22
5.1.2 The SPATRA Website.....	32
5.1.3 SPATRA Social Media Platform Channels	37
5.1.4 Press Release	40
5.2 SPATRA Communication plan	42
6 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MONITORING, KPIS AND PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT	46
6.1 Assurance of Quality of the Dissemination Results	49
7 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS.....	50

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the dissemination and communication plan for the SPATRA Project, outlining strategies to effectively communicate project results and share generated knowledge with relevant stakeholders and the wider community. The ultimate aim of the plan is to ensure the lasting impact and effective dissemination of project outcomes (eventually evolving and adapting to the progress of the developments throughout the duration of the Project, and of the relevant research and industry state-of-the-art and competition, if needed).

The plan encompasses three main components: 1. dissemination activities and tools will focus on sharing Project outcomes through various channels, 2. communication and 3. engagement activities and tools will determine and engage the target groups and the public to raise awareness of the Project research and developed solutions, thus building a solid base to support the next following exploitation activities towards the realisation of the fullest commercial potential of the Project outcomes.

The success of the Project hinges on well-coordinated efforts of the Project partners, involving or reaching out to all stakeholders, from industry experts to policymakers, and the general public. The strategy and plans employ specific described key strategic methods, like target groups mapping and segmentation, key message identification, channels, tools and material development, and monitoring and evaluation, presented in the chapter on the methodological approach.

Well-planned effective dissemination and exploitation of project outcomes are to crucially contribute to the first main WP5 objective - achieving maximum visibility and public awareness of the SPATRA developments and solutions through the implemented sound dissemination strategy, presence and participation in commercial and scientific events - as well as partially to other specific objectives detailed in Chapter 2 below. Indirectly they significantly contribute to the overall project Objective 4 (one of the main four objectives) - promoting the uptake of EU space technologies and enablement and capacity building of non-EU countries to benefit from them - and to the overall Horizon Europe programme's goal of fostering a sustainable and competitive European research and innovation ecosystem.

The dissemination and communication plans are dynamic documents that will likely undergo continuous updates to align with the Project's progress, adapting as necessary to enhance and broaden the Project's outreach to target groups and effectively communicate the vision of SPATRA. The progress, effectiveness and performance of the execution of the plans will also be continuously tracked and monitored utilizing the framework of broader standardized tools and procedures presented in Chapter 6, and the obtained feedback and lessons learned optimally used to iteratively improve and adapt the execution, or the plans themselves.

The relevant KPIs pertaining to the D&C achievements and generated results in the first quarter of the Project reported in this deliverable, have been met without deviations. Therefore, this deliverable also signifies and describes the achievement of the related important Project Milestone MS9 - initiation of the Project dissemination and communication activities and its online presence, preceded by the establishment of key necessary communication channels and tools by Month 3 of the Project.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS, ACRONYMS AND DEFINITIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
EUSPA	The European Union Agency for the Space Programme
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
DoA	Description of Action
GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
EO	Earth Observation
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
UC	Use Case
DPI	Dots Per Inch
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
UX	User Experience
UI	User Interface

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Preliminary stakeholder segmentation map on a power-interest matrix	13
Figure 2. Final-four round of candidate versions for the definitive SPATRA logo voting	23
Figure 3. Finalized SPATRA logo.....	23
Figure 4. The SPATRA colour scheme	24
Figure 5. The EU emblem and generic funding statement	25
Figure 6. PowerPoint presentation template title slide	25
Figure 7. Various typified content template slides in the PowerPoint presentation	26
Figure 8. Various typified content layout exemplified on the SPATRA deliverable template page	27
Figure 9. Printed material template - SPATRA flyer	28
Figure 10. Printed material template - SPATRA brochure.....	29
Figure 11. Printed material template - SPATRA notebook.....	29
Figure 12. Printed material template - SPATRA roll-up.....	30
Figure 13. Generic SPATRA background graphics.....	31
Figure 14. Specific graphics symbolizing the SPATRA use cases - Rail UC on the left, Road UC on the right	31
Figure 15. Banners and header backgrounds for social media platform or news posts.....	32
Figure 16. Two candidate design versions of the SPATRA website for consortial voting	34
Figure 17. Introductory banner with the Project summary on the website Homepage top section	36
Figure 18. The Project profile section on the website	36
Figure 19. The <i>Use cases</i> and <i>Partners</i> sections on the website Homepage.....	37
Figure 20. Project profile on LinkedIn	38
Figure 21. Project profile on X(Twitter).....	39
Figure 22. Project profile on Instagram.....	39
Figure 23. Title page of the initial joint press release.....	40
Figure 24. Second page of the initial joint press release	41
Figure 25. Final page of the initial joint press release	42

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Dissemination channels and tools (digital, material, and events).....	19
Table 2. Communication plan, channels and tools	43
Table 3. The standardized unified shared spreadsheet template document for reporting and tracking dissemination and communication efforts and results by all partners	46
Table 4. KPIs initially set out for the dissemination and communication effectiveness assessment	47

1 INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of WP5 encompassing this deliverable within SPATRA revolves around enhancing the project's impact through meticulously orchestrated communication, dissemination, exploitation planning and activities. These efforts amplify the scientific and technological achievements of SPATRA, engaging its audience to ultimately leverage developed IP and contribute with the pioneering outcomes to the emerging pre-standardisation efforts (on European or global level) in integrated satellite and in-situ rail/road traffic flow data.

As outlined in the SPATRA Grant Agreement (GA) Annex - Description of Action (DoA), this deliverable D5.1 presents the dissemination and communication plan of the Project, articulating a strategic blueprint for communication and dissemination drawn from the best practices advocated by the European Commission, in the formulated robust plan. According to the DoA in the GA, the joint collaborative effort of all SPATRA consortium partners, led by ZENRS, mainly in the Project Task 5.1, builds upon the preliminary draft plan presented in the Project proposal, and in this first quarterly period:

- Elaborates the plan for dissemination of Project results with all its specific outlined activities and methods for effective execution, tracking, and performance monitoring,
- Reports the activities performed by now, according to the plan,
- Formulates a communication and outreach strategy,
- Generates already some of the prerequisite assets and materials for dissemination and communication (Project website, social media channels, visual identity of the Project and some of the graphic/printed materials...), and
- Fosters the growth of an ecosystem through initial stakeholder systematisation, targeting and engagement activities (in synergy and scope of the parallel Task 5.3),

building up the necessary support to facilitate the planning of commercial exploitation of Project outcomes that is to follow and intensify in the Task 5.2.

This deliverable thus provides both the initial dissemination and communication plan of SPATRA, and the encompassed detailed portrayal of the established online presence and created distinct comprehensive visual identity of the Project (its website, social media platform channels, branding efforts, logo and presentation templates, fact sheets, press releases, leaflets, posts and news items, etc.), all aimed at the primary goal to ensure visibility of the Project and effective conveyance of its core outputs and messages to the intended target audiences. The deliverable document will be a “live/dynamic” document that will undergo continuous updates to align with the Project's progress, adapting as necessary to enhance and broaden the Project's outreach to target groups and effectively communicate the vision of SPATRA. The progress, effectiveness and performance of the execution of the plans will also be continuously tracked and monitored utilizing the framework of broader standardized tools and procedures presented in Chapter 6, and the obtained feedback and lessons learned optimally will be used to iteratively improve and adapt the execution, or the plans themselves. In addition, as stated in Chapter 6, the main instrument for tracking and monitoring the dissemination and communication (D&C) activities will be a shared spreadsheet file accessible to all partners, where they will report in standard documented form all their performed D&C efforts and generated results throughout the project duration. This shared spreadsheet is in line with the Quarterly Report template and will be examined for each Quarterly Report to be submitted to EUSPA/EC. In this way, the need for update the D&C plan will be examined every three months and necessary updates will be conducted if needed every 6 months.

Structure of this Deliverable Document

The main Chapters breakdown of this document is based on the specific objectives and main activity groups broadly listed in the section above, and specific aspects of the Project's communication and dissemination strategy and stakeholder engagement plan:

- Chapter 2 outlines the scope of reported work in the context of the overall WP5 and Project key Objectives and other related tasks, deliverables and milestones.
- Chapter 3 presents the employed methodological approach to the dissemination and communication strategy and plan definition, and ecosystem engagement (elucidating the target groups and their mapping, expected outcomes, etc.).
- Chapters 4 and 5, respectively, delve into the details of the devised dissemination and communication strategies and plans, and of the design and establishment of the relevant tools and channel methods for plan execution.
- Chapter 6 specifies the framework of instruments, including KPIs, to be utilized for continuous tracking and monitoring the progress, effectiveness and performance (and ultimately the level of success) of the execution of the plans.
- The document concludes with Chapter 7 with summary conclusions and planned next steps in WP5 and related activities.

2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

A comprehensive plan for effective dissemination and exploitation of project outcomes and the initiated relevant activities as presented in this deliverable are crucially contributing to the first and third (out of the three) main WP5 objectives:

- O5.1 - Achieving maximum visibility and public awareness of the SPATRA developments and solutions through the implemented sound dissemination strategy, presence and participation in commercial and scientific events
- O5.3 - Actively engaging with stakeholders and clients in order to anticipate scaling and closure of new business opportunities in other selected non-EU target countries (earliest preliminary activities in the scope of T5.3, as basis for exploitation to follow).

Upon achieving these objectives, they consequently aim to significantly contribute to the overall Project Objective 4 (out of its key four objectives) - *promoting the uptake of EU space technologies and enablement and capacity building of non-EU countries to benefit from them and raise awareness around Galileo, EGNOS and Copernicus applications.*

2.1 Relationship of D5.1 to Work Packages, Tasks and Milestones

Most of the work reported in this deliverable has been performed in the scope of Task 5.1, titled "Dissemination Plan and Communication Activities" - the communication strategy devised, plans for dissemination and communication defined, and digital and physical assets necessary to initiate the activities are created. This, together with performed initial efforts on engaging the stakeholders ecosystem in the scope of the Task 5.3, lays the groundwork for the Task 5.2, which is to elaborate the SPATRA exploitation plan and business model.

The submission of this deliverable introducing the dissemination plan and initiating the communication activities in the Project is thus not only of key significance for the further efforts in the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Work Package 5, but also itself alone constituting the homonymous Project Milestone MS9:

MS9	Dissemination plan and communication activities initiated	WP5	M3	D5.1 submitted
-----	---	-----	----	----------------

Best practices (including proven methods and selected appropriate tools for both intra-consortium and external communication) of the EC-endorsed communication have been leveraged in the definition of the communication and dissemination plan, aimed to be evolving and updated regularly during the project lifetime, as described in Section 1, with the first fully documented update and reporting of activities planned at M18 of the Project. The methodological approach employed in devising the strategy sets it out as also adaptable according to the feedback from monitoring, when necessary.

3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH AND TARGETS IDENTIFICATION

Considering the key relevant main objectives of the Project, towards which the WP5 efforts contribute and strive (O3 and O4), the strategy and planning of dissemination and communication is primarily driven by targeted uptake and exploitation to be achieved, also ideally tailoring and optimising the Project outputs to the targeted adopters in the process and thereby ensuring sustainability throughout and beyond the Project.

Four strategic pillars of dissemination, communication and engagement activities tackling these two main driving challenges (achieving uptake and sustainability) can be distinguished in the strategy decomposition towards detailed planning per activity types and across the timeframe and sequence of dependencies of the Project:

- **Raising awareness** - through communication: All the stakeholders relevant to SPATRA (including those in non-EU-member countries) should become aware of the aims, actions, developments and achievements of the Project, and more broadly, all the available and affected assets and resources.
- **Generating engagement** - through a variety of considered methods and instruments like initiatives, online tools, events, consultations, open science and publications, focus groups and communities of practice etc. SPATRA aims to attract and engage specific industry adopters as well innovators and potential customers and users from all over Europe, and beyond.
- **Ensuring participation** - by facilitating access to relevant information and providing direct instructive content and interaction for full and optimal understanding of SPATRA technology tools and services, insights from the testbed sites, and all key to stimulate active involvement and market uptake.
- **Enabling uptake** - by going beyond the traditional dissemination and communication plans, in gathering and disseminating evidence on the economic revenue, increased operation safety and environmental benefits of the Project assets and outputs, and embedding them in the value proposition to pave the way for exploitation beyond the end of the Project.

The first two listed pillars are in focus and primarily addressed in the initial stage covered by this deliverable, with particular importance of clear and precisely targeted communication to reach its goals. A big part of making a project successful and impactful is making sure the right stakeholders know about it and understand its results - managing and reaching out to the key adopters and groups important to the project. Each group has its own needs and preferences, so the strategy for engaging them should be customised and based on prioritisation from the start. By doing this effectively, SPATRA can make sure the key stakeholders (including the general public) are aware of the project, get their support, and use its research to make a positive difference in the areas that matter.

Precise and comprehensive identification and recognition of the relevant stakeholders important for the Project, per relevance levels and types, formally presumably mostly in scope of T5.3 (engaging the stakeholders' ecosystem), is therefore a crucial initial step prerequisite for all the following work in T5.1 and all tasks, and for all the four key strategy pillars stated above. In the following section, we will present the employed method for identifying, differentiating, and engaging the various key stakeholder groups, and who those groups are. This stakeholder systematisation exercise is planned to be repeated in the second year of the Project, in the scope of the detailed exploitation plan, and expected to refine and or expand the stakeholders map specifically focused to exploitation targets.

3.1 Stakeholder Engagement and Systematisation

To enhance growth and foster new connections throughout its duration, SPATRA will adopt an Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework. This approach aims to continually develop and strengthen relationships with key target groups, aligning with the abovementioned relevant objectives outlined in the DoA in the Grant Agreement, through three basic phases, progressively deepening engagement with target groups.

The initial phase entails scouting and evaluating potential target groups, including specific candidates relevant to SPATRA's goals and impact. Consortium members past experiences and involvement in related initiatives provide a foundation for engagement, supplemented by leads from second-degree connections and interactions with additional prospective international partners. This phase culminates in the creation of a Target Stakeholder Groups Map, organising key actors and candidates, and establishing shared terminology.

The first communication planning and execution activities had started earlier than the end of M3 of the Project, focusing on planning activities and setting up communication tools (website, social media... - see Section **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** and 5.1.3) based on and targeted to preliminarily identified potential stakeholders. Stakeholder identification and mapping remains ongoing, with flexibility to revise the plan as needed to adapt to changing circumstances. Other initial communication activities, such as press releases (Section 5.1.4), have also been carried out during this phase.

The second phase involves engaging with identified target groups, supporting activities outlined in dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategies. SPATRA collaborates with relevant initiatives on industrial digitization and may formally as a project/consortium join specific Task Forces and Working Groups (in some of which the individual partners are already involved), contribute to publications, and participate in events. Beginning in M3 of the Project, this phase is to focus on early communication activities to promote the project's presence and upcoming activities to a broader audience and specific communities. Online tools and measures are emphasised for their wide reach. Networking for webinars, articles about the project online, and other more elaborate communication activities should occur during this phase, continuing throughout the Project to communicate general aspects to a wide stakeholder base.

The third phase centres on learning from interactions and gathering external feedback to inform subsequent iterations. This involves gathering insights through quick questionnaires or interviews. Planned to begin around M7-8, when the initial outcomes are released (mainly documented requirements and defined specifications or architecture/methodology), targeted communication activities focus on specific project outcomes and benefits. These activities include producing and communicating articles, blogs, or posts, hosting online events to consult the influencing stakeholders and groups, get feedback or co-design, and eventually creating optional targeted communication materials like videos. This phase runs concurrently with the second phase, emphasising the communication of specific project outcomes and benefits to target groups.

3.1.1 SPATRA Stakeholders Mapping and Segmentation

Figure 1 below displays the initial version of the SPATRA Stakeholders Map, summarising the primary target audiences at this stage. The power-interest diagram positions the primarily important target stakeholder groups identified thus far, evolving from ongoing work, as multi-coloured textboxes/stickers. It is a basic framework for organising target groups according to their level of interest and influence, as follows:

- The horizontal axis represents the interest each target group has in the Project developments and outputs, and vice versa (the interest of the Project in targeting the specific group/role as an adopter of results and outputs).
- The vertical axis represents the power or influence each group may exert on the Project developments and potential impact, and vice versa.

Figure 1. Preliminary stakeholder segmentation map on a power-interest matrix

The overall resulting impact of specific groups onto the Project will in reality also depend significantly and be compounded by the interest they show in the Project, which at this early stage is not yet reliably expressed or captured, and will get more precisely assessed as the Project progresses and the relevant stakeholders get more informed and familiar with it.

On the diagram in Figure 1, the simplest matrix background layout area is divided to four equal quadrants denoting (in grey big captions) additionally the segmentation of the belonging stakeholder groups per distinct

combined power-interest level ranges, and consequently common resulting prioritisation scenarios for the Project in targeting and satisfying the stakeholder needs and interests (“what” to do for “whom”), as follows:

- **“Manage Closely”** (top right) Quadrant

The "Manage Closely" quadrant denotes stakeholders with significant influence on the Project and a strong interest in its outcomes. These target groups are pivotal to the Project's success and necessitate early engagement and regular communication to ensure their feedback is incorporated throughout the project.

- **“Keep Satisfied”** (top left) Quadrant

The "Keep Satisfied" quadrant comprises stakeholders with decision-making authority but limited availability or interest to actively participate or fully follow the Project. While maintaining consistent communication with this group may pose challenges, their feedback should be acknowledged, and the project should align its activities with their directives.

- **“Keep Informed”** (bottom right) Quadrant

The "Keep Informed" quadrant encompasses organisations or individuals closely associated with the Project, but with minimal impact or influence on its outcomes. While the synergy between these groups and the project may be limited, exploring collaborative communication and dissemination efforts can be advantageous.

- **“Monitor”** (bottom left) Quadrant

The "Monitor" quadrant includes organisations, individuals, or associations with low influence on project activities and limited availability to engage in them. These target groups are not expected to be extensively involved in project activities. However, the project should maintain regular communication with them and remain vigilant if they transition to other quadrants.

Within SPATRA, both main high-impact and additional low-impact stakeholders have been identified. As evident, this early initial segmentation has concentrated on the stakeholder groups and types known or perceived to be most influential and important for the Project (as shown on the diagram above), which are the following:

- **Transport and logistics companies**

Transport and logistics companies, as stakeholders in the road use case, comprise organisations involved in transporting goods and materials. This includes freight forwarders, carriers, logistics service providers, and related entities. In the context of the SPATRA project, logistics companies are vital stakeholders for sharing information and communication efforts, as they have a vested interest in improving transportation routes, efficiency, and reducing costs. Engaging with logistics companies can foster collaboration and support for the project, while also increasing visibility and credibility within the industry. These stakeholders may be keen on participating in project events, such as industry forums and workshops, to stay informed about the latest advancements and network with peers. They may also find value in project publications, webinars, or newsletters that share insights and progress relevant to their operations.

- **(Rail) Infrastructure managers**

Rail infrastructure managers represent key stakeholders in the rail transport use case, overseeing the maintenance, operation, and development of railway infrastructure, including tracks, stations, and signalling systems. This category includes entities responsible for managing national rail networks, regional rail systems, and other railway infrastructure assets. In the context of the SPATRA project, rail infrastructure managers play a pivotal role in the deployment and integration of satellite-based solutions to improve rail operations and safety. Engaging with rail infrastructure managers is essential for garnering support, fostering collaboration, and ensuring alignment with industry standards and regulations. These stakeholders may be interested in participating in project workshops, conferences, or working groups focused on rail innovation and technology. Moreover, they may seek out project updates and technical insights through publications, webinars, or other communication channels tailored to the rail sector's specific needs and challenges. Managers of road-related infrastructure (like border-area freight parking or warehousing facilities) are also of interest, but rail infrastructure managers have been specifically identified as most significant target stakeholders in infrastructure management.

- **Local authorities, Government agencies**

The knowledge and EO data harnessed in the Project can be used by the local authorities for improving the understanding and forecasting of the mobility patterns in the border areas, enabling them to make more targeted and effective interventions. The decision-makers responsible for transportation or urban planning could use valuable insights from SPATRA to help them make more informed decisions and improve traffic flow management.

- **Research/Academia**

The Project will engage with active researchers in the EO and its application fields, as well as in logistics and transport research and other general related fields (computer vision, machine learning, EO-based data analysis), to support the knowledge transfer. This category of active researchers includes research-oriented institutions (technical universities, RTOs, spin-offs) and individuals, as well as business-driven organisations (from high-risk-taking startups to innovation units in large-scale industry) that may contribute to the technical ambition of the project and will represent the main target audience for reusing the research outcomes.

- **Solution Providers**

This group has some overlapping and same constituents as the Research/Academia above, mainly the RTOs and business-driven research organisations (startups, spin-offs) reusing or developing further the research outcomes of the Project, but “solutions” in this context denotes strictly commercial and market-oriented solutions, and their providers, targeted also as potential integrators or licensed 3rd party developers or adapters of the Project results like tools, modules or datasets. Again, the same as the Research/Academia above, they are also a major targeted audience for reusing the research and development outcomes of the Project, potentially with even higher significance and impact as it extends over the industry.

- **Thematic Communities and Groups**

Relevant working groups and task forces with already active participation of the individual consortium partners bring together existing community efforts to drive common discussions, strategies and advancements, including joint contributions to standardisation, also one of the Project goals. Relevant examples, where the Project has set out to capitalise on consolidated activities from the start, are the

OGC Working Groups² (such as OGC City Geography Markup Language (CityGML) WG, with Zentrix already a member) in the EO application domains, or Transport Community³ (including partners from EU-member and 6 Western Balkans countries working on integrating their transport markets into the EU, with UNI already a member) in the transport domain.

- **General Public**

Outcomes of the Project could benefit the general public by improving the flow of traffic and reducing congestion and pollution, thereby enhancing the private transport and quality of life in near-border and urban areas. And it is generally good for every project, particularly if involved in surveillance and monitoring of public areas and infrastructure, to have a favourable stance and clear interest of the general public.

Some of the additional stakeholder groups mentioned as examples in the explanation under the diagram (like related initiatives, specific communities, task forces or bodies) will mostly populate the bottom quadrants on the diagram with lower non-critical combined impact on the Project, and their exact levels of interest and influence (and positioning on the diagram) is left to be determined after direct liaisons with them.

3.1.2 SPATRA Focus Groups

To boost engagement with target stakeholder groups, in the scope of T5.3 we are in the process of establishing focus groups comprising external experts drawn from the key target stakeholder types. These groups should play a crucial role in tailoring the communication, dissemination and exploitation planning activities of the Project to meet the specific needs and interests of the target groups, thereby enhancing SPATRA's impact, success and sustainability. The insights and feedback provided by focus group members can assist the project team in refining the communication and dissemination strategy to effectively engage the target groups. They can offer valuable suggestions and guidance to the consortium on focus areas from a professional standpoint, contributing to the Project's objectives and ultimately increased uptake.

The potential target fields for sourcing the focus group expert members include primarily land transport and logistics, and specifically railway infrastructure, the key identified prospective adopter areas as stated above. A dedicated thematic focus group (or even two), just from the road and rail transport/logistics fields are initially considered at this stage. Further potential fields of interest for drawing the focus group membership would be spatial/urban planning, environmental and water, aerospace, automotive, construction, electronics, and military.

Focus group members are expected to be proactive, possessing strong technical/scientific and security backgrounds, and have experience participating in EU projects. This ensures they can readily comprehend the project and its objectives and make an immediate impact. The responsibilities of focus group members include:

- Familiarising themselves with the Project and its objectives,
- Participating in consortium meetings (one meeting per year), and optimally also workshops,
- Providing their perspectives on the Project and exploitation,

Offering suggestions and advice to the consortium on focus areas from a professional standpoint and contributing to the Project objectives.

² <https://www.ogc.org/about-ogc/committees/swg>

³ <https://www.transport-community.org>

4 SPATRA DISSEMINATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

The dissemination plan outlines the various activities, measures, tools and channels that will be established and used to effectively communicate the Project's results to the target groups, with the aim of creating and constantly increasing awareness and understanding, and encouraging engagement actions. The plan will utilise a range of defined tools and activities to disseminate results to target groups, achieving them through traditional and hybrid online media. The dissemination and engagement activities are critical for ensuring that target groups are aware of SPATRA innovations and results, and getting attracted and engaged with the Project, according to first two strategic pillars set out in the methodology in Chapter 3 above, and ultimately maximising the Project's impact. The plan outlines dissemination channels and asset mechanisms used to disseminate the SPATRA results: dedicated sections on the Project website, dissemination guidelines, peer-reviewed scientific and technical publications, position papers, blogs, and other non-scientific publications, training materials and webinars, participation at conferences and workshops, and open access repositories to publish research results. The Description of Action has defined Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for each activity type and the monitoring tools to track the effectiveness of each used means of dissemination. These are presented in the relevant Chapter 6 further below.

In temporal planning and implementation, the D&C strategy of the Project adopts a comprehensive 4-aspect approach that revolves around the key questions of “*what, when, to whom, and how?*”. This approach is designed to ensure effective outreach by all consortium resources, optimally orchestrated throughout the Project, with partners encouraged to follow all the needed steps, select relevant aspects, and augment their efforts to maximise audience engagement.

The established dissemination objectives are closely interlinked with communication objectives and the overall Project objectives, as described in Chapter 2 above, with the general overarching aim of the dissemination plan is to maximise the impact of the project outcomes and to reach a wide range of target groups, in line with the objectives of Horizon Europe. While the dissemination and communication plans are closely linked, the minor key difference is that the next two dissemination phases following this starting ***Analysis and Initiation*** one (***Interaction*** and ***Learning and Optimization***, as set out in the Project proposal, answering mainly to the “*what?*” and “*how?*” key strategic questions above) are more determined in distinct scope and timeframe, whereas in the communication plan they are more intertwined, spanning the entire remaining Project duration. It is however possible to extend or adjust the scope and planned execution periods of the dissemination phases, if necessary, particularly the last third one.

In additional synergy with the stakeholder engagement Task 5.3, we plan to share the relevant outcomes of the Project with media outlets across the EU and non-EU professional press at national levels through press releases and articles, and other describing/supporting materials (mainly tailored non-scientific publications). The goal is to raise awareness about SPATRA (in earlier stage) and promote the Project's findings (in later stage), emphasising the challenges and solutions for target groups. Relevant EU media channels, including specialised press, have been preliminarily identified (such as the EC-hosted *CORDIS Research*EU Magazine*, or the *iThink Media Innovation (formerly Digital Innovation) Magazine*), and partners will assist in continuous expansion of the list, identifying media contacts at national levels, and translations of media pieces will be arranged where necessary, to ensure maximum visibility for the Project. Graphic tools such as infographics will be utilized to support media activities wherever feasible, and identifying, reaching out, and directly engaging the relevant influential journalists and bloggers in each consortium partner or member state who have written about topics related to the project will also be considered.

Targeted baseline level of non-scientific publication activities in total has been set to at least 20 releases or contributions to articles, position papers, blog posts or others over the course of the project, including “success interviews” with community leaders, in addition to articles and editorials written for the newsletter and the Project website with partner support.

In terms of scientific publications, the project intends to demonstrate research findings and raise awareness in the research and industry communities mainly through publications in scientific and technical literature and dedicated journals. Papers will be presented at conferences and other events to increase project visibility and constructive sharing of the results and outcomes.

Additionally, events carried out in other work packages of the Project will be utilized to promote the project and its outcomes. Partners are committed to present the SPATRA project at conferences, workshops, and fairs at national, European, and global levels, also striving to connect with other related EU-funded projects. For partners traveling to attend events, an active role at those events is recommended, such as hosting an information stand, delivering presentations, or conducting meetings with key target groups. Partners will use already graphically designed and templated brochures, posters/roll-ups, presentations, later optionally video material of Project solutions and piloting in action, and can request support from the WP5 team for the design of necessary graphics, ensuring they are tailored to the audience (though this work has already comprehensively underway and generating diverse assets, as detailed in the relevant Section 5.1 further below).

As noted above, the partners are required to report and document their participation using monitoring tools (Chapter 6 below). After participating in events, they will communicate tentative numbers of participants, presentations, or website links, target groups reached, and more, to be added to the monitoring file. Some relevant conferences have already been attended, and potential next upcoming ones identified and also entered in the common shared planning template that will be regularly updated and assessed for optimizing prospective participations and attendances (in terms of partners complementarities, overlappings, and sharing the costs and resources). Additionally, project partners will contribute to wider common information, dissemination and exploitation planning activities (such as projects clustering and networks) to increase visibility and synergies between other Horizon Europe actions, should they be invited by the European Commission.

4.1 Dissemination Channels and Tools (Digital, Printed and Events)

SPATRA reaches towards the identified diverse stakeholder groups (across academia, industry professionals, authorities and policymakers, to the general public), segmented and prioritized as specified in the Section 3.1.1 above, using a correspondingly broad and diverse range and mix of dissemination and communication methods and tools, many of which serve both purposes. All the relevant means and methods will therefore be covered, combined in this and the corresponding Section 5.1 in the chapter on communication further below, and the channels and tools intended to be specifically dedicated to dissemination and spreading information are the following:

Table 1. Dissemination channels and tools (digital, material, and events)

What?	Why?	How?	For Whom?
Shared Project documentation (deliverables, white papers, guidelines & recommendations)	To describe and report on technical outputs (APIs, architectures, models), promote guidelines, insights or recommendations, etc.	Via the Project website, links and references on social media channels, online cloud repositories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport and logistics companies • Infrastructure Managers • Government agencies • Local authorities • Solution providers
Peer-reviewed scientific or technical publications	To ensure the technical achievements and experimental findings of the Project get known and exploited by the larger research community and related scientific domains.	<p>At least one peer-reviewed scientific paper in journals and two in conferences, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remote Sensing • IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems • Journal of Advanced Transportation • Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit • IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference • European Transport Conference • International Conference on Transportation and Development, <p>or equivalent top refereed scientific/technical journals and conferences in relevant fields</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research/Academia • Solution providers
Non-scientific publications and media	To widespread and promote awareness and validation of the results, thus directly and indirectly enabling and increasing uptake among broadest target audiences.	<p>At least 20 releases of, or contributions to, articles, position papers, blog posts or other non-scientific publication over the course of the Project, oriented to end-users (or to all in the general society benefiting from the SPATRA outcomes uptake), including "success</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport and logistics companies • Infrastructure Managers • Government agencies • Local authorities • Solution providers

		<p>interviews" with pilot site or community leaders. Reference media for publications could be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC CORDIS Research*EU Magazine • EC TRIMIS Information Portal • iThink Media Innovation (formerly Digital Innovation) Magazine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public
Open Access to research	<p>To expand the exploitation, cross-validation, and further experimentation and improvement potential of technical and data achievements and results of the Project by the larger research community and the industries (under appropriate access restrictions), enabling them access to datasets and additional digital resources, along with the peer-reviewed publications.</p>	<p>SPATRA will facilitate an online repository to manage and publish material with different access permissions, including peer-reviewed publications, shareable scientific research data, and other types of resources, aiming to generate over 500 downloads. The Project will rely on Zenodo – part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) – to deposit both publications and datasets or models. The use of Open Research Europe will also be encouraged, as an open access publishing platform for scientific articles among the consortium, without author fees. Whenever possible, the datasets will as well be made openly available via the data.europa.eu, the official portal for EU data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research/Academia • Transport and logistics companies • Infrastructure Managers • Government agencies • Local authorities • Solution providers
Webinars	<p>To transfer and exchange technical and socio-economic knowledge with the targeted communities.</p>	<p>SPATRA will (co-)organise two webinars during the Project's lifetime, with a targeted total of 50 unique participants. Events will be public, with sessions hosted, recorded, edited, and ultimately uploaded as educational multimedia resources and knowledge pills for each training itinerary.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types
Conferences /Congresses	<p>As a strategic mechanism to interact</p>	<p>The consortium will showcase the Project concepts and results</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types

/Fairs	most actively and intensely with the largest number and range of multiple stakeholders in a short time, at regional/local, European, or wider international or global levels.	through presentations, talks, exhibition spaces and personal engagement, participating in at least 3 relevant events . The preliminary identified prospective events are the following, strongly related to the edge continuum and its space-based industrial applications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • InnoTrans 2024, Berlin • SpaceTechExpo Europe 2024, Bremen • RAILCON 2024 in Niš, Serbia (here a workshop will be organized) • Intermodal Europe 2024 • Transport Logistic 2025 • IGARSS 2025, Brisbane • Multimodal 2024 • IANA Intermodal Expo 	
Thematic Communities and Groups	Participation in working groups etc. bring together existing community efforts to drive common discussions, strategies and advancements, including joint contributions to standardisation.	This is a specific stakeholder supertype comprising engaged representatives mainly from the targeted stakeholder types listed on the right, and the planned engagement actions and identified preliminary target groups and communities have been specified in the definition in Section 3.1.1 above.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport and logistics companies • Government agencies • Local authorities • Solution providers

Specific details of the dissemination plan, as provided in the "**How?**" column in the table above for channels and means like future-targeted peer-reviewed and other publication media, or events planned for participation, are evolving elements of the plan, being expanded or updated over time depending on the state of developments in the Project or strategy adjustments, and are as such being documented and tracked versioned in the created and live shared plan files, integrated with the internal monitoring and tracking instruments described in the related Chapter 6 further below. All the KPIs defined for monitoring, quantifying and assessing the performance of the dissemination and communication activities to be carried out are also fully listed there, with some already emphasized in **bold text** in the content of the "How?" column in the table above.

5 SPATRA COMMUNICATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

The strategy begins with establishing the Project's visual identity and identifying the appropriate communication channels and formulating the plan (*Analysis and Initiation* stage), and subsequently completing all the necessary Project communication tools, with most efforts and authorship by the Task (and WP) leading partner.

The following combined *Interaction* and *Learning and Optimization* stages involve all the partners with more balanced intensified efforts in the execution of planned activities in synergy with the dissemination, continuously adapting and improving the execution of communication actions (and the plan if necessary) based on the feedback and reactions from the targeted stakeholders and audiences obtained through all two-way communication means and channels. These will involve designing and implementing campaigns to promote the Project and its outcomes throughout its lifetime, efficiently building traction among the target audiences and capitalising on the multilingual nature of the consortium to cover an international footprint and contribute to the uptake and exploitation. The campaigns will build upon the promotion mix that focuses on the strategic pillars of creating and increasing awareness, and engaging and persuading the audiences, as set out in the methodology chapter above.

The strategy also involves reaching out to target thematic groups, communities and partner organizations in related fields by leveraging the networks of the Project partners, complementing the initially identified target engagement selection specified in the Section 3.1.1 above, and to be continuously evaluated and updated as needed. All partners are encouraged to stay informed and involved in most activity types to enhance performance, and the tools are being developed aiming also to facilitate the dissemination of progress and major events, all towards the overall goal to ultimately reach the critical mass and interest level for the uptake, and achieve the set KPIs.

5.1 Established SPATRA Communication Tools and Channels

5.1.1 Logo and Visual Identity

An important step in guiding SPATRA towards success consistently is to define and design the Project's visual identity, including the logo and its variations, as well as the colour scheme and font selection.

In this respect, the relevant "branding and merchandising" requirements for the visual identity set out for SPATRA since the project proposal stage are somewhat specific and not typical for most Horizon Research & Innovation Actions projects - mainly the strong overall Project emphasis on pilot validation use cases and needed material visibility and recognizability on-site and in fieldwork. That implies specific tailored functional design measures, such as:

- all the key graphic identity elements needing to be as prominently clear and legible as possible, ideally noticeable and robust even in sub-optimal weather or visibility conditions, or when partially scratched or damaged, which in turn calls for practical steps like:
 - selecting strong or contrasting colour schemes, combinations and geometry, suitable for printing using simpler and more robust techniques (like silkscreen, rubber pad, transfer, or stamping),
 - avoiding complex detailed shapes or colour gradients,
 - supporting optional printing of key visual elements in fluorescent colours, while maintaining the same graphic identity,
 - etc.
- specific appealing dedicated graphics symbolizing the two pilot use cases

- the aim to explore appealing and sustainable (after the Project) brand graphics ranging from quite big (stickers or direct printing on vehicles and freight transportation means, printed T-shirts) to very small sizes and formats (prints on memory sticks) requires the key graphic elements to be adapted for significant scalability, both enlargement and downsizing.

Having the general as well as these specific requirements and design directions in mind, the brainstorming and conceptual design process resulted with four candidate variants for the definitive voting procedure for the Project logo after the last round of preliminary selection:

Figure 2. Final-four round of candidate versions for the definitive SPATRA logo voting

The leftmost option had received the most votes, followed by the rightmost, and was consequently selected, and further fine-tuned to obtain the final design, characterized by strong sans-serif legible typeface suitable for scaling and uniformly coloured dynamic shapes and colours symbolizing Earth Observation, and roads and rails, all adequate for simple silkscreen or pad printing in two-colour passes:

Figure 3. Finalized SPATRA logo

The Colour Scheme

Driven mainly by the specific functional design requirements mentioned above in the previous section, two basic minimalistic palettes have been selected, each a combination of a striking primary accent colour and a secondary neutral gray in warm and cool options (**Figure 4** below).

As evident, the primary palette combination is on the logo, and the primary accent colours in both palettes, pale green and magenta, are suitable for

fluorescent equivalents printing for attractive on-vehicle and general outdoor applications, in which the grays can as well be substituted by silver, applicable also on dark backgrounds.

Primary Color Palette

Secondary Color Palette

Figure 4. The SPATRA colour scheme

These colour palettes are intended to constitute the main colouring used in all SPATRA graphics, as will be presented further.

The EU Funding Acknowledgement/Impressum

Following the European Commission's guidelines on corporate visual identity, communication efforts by recipients of the grant associated with the initiative (which may include media engagements, seminars, conferences, information materials such as electronic brochures, posters, presentations, etc.), dissemination strategies, and any supported infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies, or significant outcomes must recognize the support provided by the EU by showcasing the European flag (emblem) and the funding statement (

Figure 5), which in full form states:

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101129658."

Additionally, these acknowledgments must be translated into local languages when deemed necessary.

Figure 5. The EU emblem and generic funding statement

The SPATRA Templates and Modular Re-usable Graphic Elements

In the scope of T5.1, templates have been designed for the main commonly and frequently used documents in the Project - deliverables (and other reports) and PowerPoint presentations - to visually (and in terms of layout) standardize the Project communication, in both mandatory official and in less formal representative documented communication towards key institutional stakeholders, primarily the funding authorities.

Figure 6. PowerPoint presentation template title slide

List Style

- At vero eos et accusamus et iusto odio dignissimos ducimus qui blanditiis praesentium voluptatum deleniti atque corrupti quos dolores et quas molestias excepturi sint occaecati cupiditate non provident
- At vero eos et accusamus et iusto odio dignissimos ducimus qui blanditiis praesentium voluptatum deleniti atque corrupti quos dolores et quas molestias excepturi sint occaecati cupiditate non provident
- At vero eos et accusamus et iusto odio dignissimos ducimus qui blanditiis praesentium voluptatum deleniti atque corrupti quos dolores et quas molestias excepturi sint occaecati cupiditate non provident
- At vero eos et accusamus et iusto odio dignissimos ducimus qui blanditiis praesentium voluptatum deleniti atque corrupti quos dolores et quas molestias excepturi sint occaecati cupiditate non provident
- At vero eos et accusamus et iusto odio dignissimos ducimus qui blanditiis praesentium voluptatum deleniti atque corrupti quos dolores et quas molestias excepturi sint occaecati cupiditate non provident
- At vero eos et accusamus et iusto odio dignissimos ducimus qui blanditiis praesentium voluptatum deleniti atque corrupti quos dolores et quas molestias excepturi sint occaecati cupiditate non provident

Neque porro quisquam est, qui dolorem ipsum quia dolor sit amet

Neque porro quisquam est, qui dolorem ipsum quia dolor sit amet

Neque porro quisquam est, qui dolorem ipsum quia dolor sit amet

Timeline

Figure 7. Various typified content template slides in the PowerPoint presentation

1. Heading technical part of this deliverable report

Text ...

2.1 Subheading 1

Text ...

2.1.1 Subheading 2

Text ...

Table 1. Title of the table

Nunc	Nunc (1)	Nunc	Nunc	Nunc
Nulla	Nulla	Nulla	Nulla	Nulla
Nulla	Nulla	Nulla (2)	Nulla	Nulla

(1) This is a table note.

(2) And this is another table note.

2.1.1.1 Subheading 3

Text ...

2.1.1.2 Subheading 4

Text ...

Figure 1. Simplified diagram of the convergence model

Source: JRC, Eurostat, 2016.

Text ...

This is an equation $(x + a)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^k a^{n-k}$

Figure 8. Various typified content layout exemplified on the SPATRA deliverable template page

These templates feature the additional blue colour palette over the standard colour scheme given in Section The Colour Scheme above, linking visually to the European emblem and denoting more formality.

Example of the designed Project deliverable template is this document, though the template contains additional diverse example layouts for different types of content (nested lists, equations and formulas, diagrams, etc., as shown on **Figure 8** above) expected and commonly found in all the technical and other deliverables.

Templates with basic conceptual layouts have also been produced for the promotional and presentational graphic material and document types intended mainly to be printed - the SPATRA brochure, flyer, and roll-up/poster, presented on the figures below - though there is still no sufficient complete and agreed content for these, just titles or section subtitles and basic descriptions from the Project profile.

Figure 9. Printed material template - SPATRA flyer

Figure 10. Printed material template - SPATRA brochure

Figure 11. Printed material template - SPATRA notebook

Templating and modularity of the designed graphic standards and identity of the Project extends also to the planned "merchandising" printed material, as mentioned in the introduction of the visual identity section above, with an example being the rugged metal-binder notebook presented on **Figure 11** above, intended to be handed out primarily in the workshop (or event/meeting) kit, but also potentially useful for taking notes on-site and in field work.

Figure 12. Printed material template - SPATRA roll-up

The templating design efforts are continuous and ongoing in T5.1, and more new templates are likely to be created, tailored to eventual additional specific identified needs, purposes, or communication targets (including upon requests of the consortium partners to the WP5 team). The same is the case with designing other various typified graphical elements or fragments, like backgrounds, banners, vignettes, etc., the results produced by now shown on the figures below. Some of these elements have been initially designed around a specific focused purpose or visually presented motif (like the graphics symbolizing the two SPATRA pilot validation use cases on **Figure 14**, or banners for social media posts on **Figure 15** below), but have subsequently been found reusable and spread to additional purposes. As evident from figures presented in this complete chapter,

the modular graphic elements described here are notably re-used and appearing in the document templates, website and social media platform posts, newsletter, printed materials, and across multiple communication channels and tools, benefiting from the generally clean and modular design concept followed from the start.

Figure 13. Generic SPATRA background graphics

Figure 14. Specific graphics symbolizing the SPATRA use cases - Rail UC on the left, Road UC on the right
(example in the relevant context on the website also on **Figure 19** further below)

Figure 15. Banners and header backgrounds for social media platform or news posts

5.1.2 The SPATRA Website

A website serves as a valuable tool for interactive project communication, offering a centralised fully managed platform to share information, involve target groups, and boost project visibility. Some of the goals facilitated by the website, and key advantages over most of the other D&C channels and tools, include:

- Reaching a broader audience: Websites allow access to a larger audience compared to traditional methods like print materials or in-person events. It provides an easy way to disseminate information globally to anyone with internet access.
- Least effort in sharing information: Websites offer a centralized hub where target groups can access project details and shared resources such as goals, activities, and outcomes. This saves time and resources in information management, generation and editing, compared to distributing information through multiple channels.
- Highlighting project impact: Websites enable the highlighting of project impact through success stories, testimonials, and multimedia, aiding in garnering support and attracting potential partners or funders.
- Engaging target groups: Websites provide a platform to engage various target groups including partners, community members, and the public, through feedback mechanisms, discussion forums, and social media platform integration.
- Boosting project visibility: Websites contribute to improving projects visibility by enhancing search engine rankings and facilitating sharing across social media and other online platforms.
- Providing project updates: Websites offer a centralised space for accessing project updates like progress reports, news articles, and event information, ensuring continuous engagement and information dissemination.
- Enhancing project credibility: Websites help bolster project credibility by presenting a professional online presence (if thoroughly maintained and kept up to date) and showcasing team expertise and achievements.

In the same iterative collaborative design process methodology as employed for the creation of the Project visual identity and other tools and channels, two conceptual designs had been proposed for the SPATRA website (**Figure 16**), both aligned with the Project's objectives and the defined visual identity and design requirements and principles, to effectively communicate and interact with the target audiences. The collaborative process of selecting, voting for, and continuously refining the website design reflects the consortium's commitment to creating a platform that best serves the needs of stakeholders and enhances the project's overall impact and visibility, and version one (on the left in **Figure 16**) has been chosen for implementation.

The initial release has in the meantime been performed, available on the <https://spatra-project.eu/> Project domain.

The running website is since being continuously gradually filled with relevant content sections, in a joint effort by all contributing partners, and with an extra editorial check and correction or verification step by the WP5 leader or the Project coordinator for each partner-authored content or post, to ensure quality and alignment with the Project vision and objectives, as the website will be a crucial tool for the Project outreach and outcomes sharing, offering a central hub to disseminate information, engage target groups, and enhance project visibility and impact.

Some of the targeted more comprehensive technical and UX site performance features (fully mobile-friendly design and inclusive accessibility, tracking analytics, search engine optimisation, or detailed content integration with social media) are in continuous development or being set up.

Figure 16. Two candidate design versions of the SPATRA website for consortia voting

The website structure will be periodically updated to meet project needs, with the initial version following this layout:

Website Map

- **Homepage:**
 - **Introductory Banner and Project Summary**
 - **About the Project**
 - **About the SPATRA Project (profile)**
 - **Innovation and Impact**
 - **Use Cases**
 - **Use Case 1 – Road**
 - **Use Case 2 – Rail**
 - **Meet the Partners** (list page)
 - **Latest News Feed**
 - **Subscription Section**
- **Master Header Navigation** (additional to the listed above, already in the Homepage content):
 - **Partners** - detailed profile page for each partner with their info and role in the Project
 - **Resources**
 - **Deliverables**
 - **Publications**
 - **Resources** - datasets, media (flyer, brochure, presentations, etc.)
 - **News** - complete archive of all published news on project progress and achievements (not just the latest)
 - **Blog** - posts providing insights into research findings, technological advancements, and industry implications
 - **Events and Workshops** - upcoming and past events, workshops, webinars, and meetings
 - **Newsletter Archive**
 - **Contact** - information of the coordinating and technical managing partner, and the form for inquiries related to collaboration, press, and general questions about the Project

Figure 17. Introductory banner with the Project summary on the website Homepage top section

Figure 18. The Project profile section on the website

Figure 19. The *Use cases* and *Partners* sections on the website Homepage

Publishing SPATRA related information on partners’ websites

In addition to project website as a valuable tool for interactive project communication, the SPATRA partners will also publish information on the SPATRA activities on their websites to raise the awareness of all stakeholders. The minimum information to be published on partners’ websites will include project framework and objectives, list of project partners, and links to online resources of the project.

5.1.3 SPATRA Social Media Platform Channels

Social media platforms like LinkedIn and X (Twitter) are increasingly important for researchers and developers to connect with peers, share ideas, and spread their work. In this digital age, it's crucial for researchers to have a solid social media presence, as it allows them to showcase their expertise, grow their networks, and boost the visibility of their research.

LinkedIn serves as a professional platform where researchers can create profiles highlighting their education, research interests, publications, and professional experience. By connecting with peers in their field, researchers can expand their networks and establish collaborations that may lead to new projects and funding opportunities. LinkedIn also offers a space for researchers to share their findings, discuss emerging trends, and engage with others in their field.

Twitter, on the other hand, is a micro-blogging platform enabling users to share short messages (tweets) with followers. Researchers utilize Twitter to share findings, promote publications, and connect with peers. It also provides an avenue to engage with non-academic audiences such as policymakers and journalists. By using hashtags, researchers can join conversations related to their work and contribute to public discourse.

Both LinkedIn and Twitter offer unique features valuable to researchers. LinkedIn is ideal for building professional networks and collaborations, while Twitter focuses on sharing timely updates and engaging a broader audience. Researchers can use both platforms together to strengthen their online presence, expand networks, and promote their research. Embracing social media as a tool for research advancement is essential in today's digital world, allowing researchers to reach wider audiences and make an impact in their fields.

Created SPATRA social media channel accounts and profiles are:

1. LinkedIn - <https://www.linkedin.com/company/spatra-project/>
2. X (Twitter) - <https://twitter.com/spatraproject>
3. Instagram – <https://www.instagram.com/spatraproject>

and are active, with posting and campaigning activities underway.

Figure 20. Project profile on LinkedIn

Figure 21. Project profile on X(Twitter)

Figure 22. Project profile on Instagram

5.1.4 Press Release

The inaugural joint press release informing about the start of the project has been completed and approved for distribution and publication by the Project Officer from the EC side, in the final form as shown on the figures below:

Figure 23. Title page of the initial joint press release

Collaborative Efforts for a Sustainable Future

With the collaborative strength of international partners and the backing of the EU's space program, SPATRA is committed to delivering close to market-ready solutions that will not only benefit the European logistic and railway sectors but also have a global impact.

Tailored Solutions for Real-World Challenges

The project has outlined specific use cases to demonstrate SPATRA's approach to overcoming challenges within the transport sector:

- **Efficient Road Traffic Management:** SPATRA is developing satellite-based tools to analyze real-time traffic data, aiming to enhance traffic flow management. This is particularly crucial at border crossings where delays are common, potentially leading to reduced waiting times and more efficient logistics.
- **Rail Safety Enhancements:** The project is employing satellite data to anticipate and mitigate risks associated with rail infrastructure, such as track buckling due to extreme temperatures. This focus on improvement of rail safety aims to provide more reliable rail services across Europe.

Figure 24. Second page of the initial joint press release

Commitment to Sustainable and Safe Transport

SPATRA is committed to making transport systems more efficient, safe, and environmentally friendly. By leveraging space technologies, the project supports the European Green Deal's objectives, showcasing the impactful role of these technologies in transforming transport.

Join the SPATRA Journey

Stakeholders, policymakers, and the public are invited to engage with SPATRA's progress and contribute to shaping a sustainable transport future in Europe.

Follow SPATRA Project on social media platforms:

[Linkedin](#) [X](#) [Instagram](#)

SPATRA Project website is coming soon and will be available at:

<https://spatra-project.eu/>

For further details and to get involved, please reach out to our Project Communications Manager at:

Jelena Vasic, Director of Marketing & Communications | Zentrix Lab

jelena.vasic@zentrixlab.eu

+381 63 7257336

Figure 25. Final page of the initial joint press release

5.2 SPATRA Communication plan

This section provides a systematic summary of the wide range of communication channels, tools and activities planned in the SPATRA project (from traditional ones like websites, flyers and brochures, newsletters, or email campaigns, to emerging social media platforms), including the various described in the previous section above that have already been created and active. The breakdown per targeted stakeholder types (for whom?),

employed methods and means (how?), and purposes and goals (why?), elaborates how each different communication channel/tool has been defined to reach the relevant target groups in ways that optimally suit their respective audiences, similar as for the dissemination plan in the previous chapter above.

These channels, tools and activities are to inform and generate professional, industry, academic and public target group interest in the project, its results, and EU support, with some of the relevant performance indicators briefly mentioned in the "How?" column, and listed in full in the next chapter.

Communication activities play a vital role in leveraging the results of the project, ensuring that target groups are aware of SPATRA innovations during the project's lifespan, and helping to pave the way for exploitation and our solutions and services in the market afterwards. The activities also encompass specific measures to promote the project and its results to the wider public. Jointly with engagement activities in scope of T5.3 campaigns will be designed and executed throughout the project lifetime to engage the target audiences effectively, leveraging the consortium's multilingual capabilities to reach an international audience. These campaigns will build upon the Promotion Mix, focusing on creating awareness and persuading the audience. The communication plan is outlined in the table below.

Table 2. Communication plan, channels and tools

What?	Why?	How?	For Whom?
Personal channel - e-mail campaigns	Personal measure with expected high qualitative effect for promoting actions and results, relevant to reaching out to end-users, key technology communities, and engaging with practically all the target partnerships and networks.	Broadcasting messages to a database of contact points (the goal is to reach 500 contact points), preferably using a GDPR-compliant solution like Brevo (formerly Sendinblue) ⁴ and differently designed templates fit to the specific target groups, and integrating call-to-action measures to increase engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types

⁴ <https://www.brevo.com/gdpr>

<p>Personal channel - one-to-one meetings</p>	<p>Individual meetings are effective in interaction with relevant individuals, often as a follow-up of e-mail exchange, scouting efforts, events or coaching. This engagement strategy will primarily target infrastructure and logistic managers, to amplify the outreach capacity or seek business opportunity.</p>	<p>The project will communicate with at least 5 companies from logistics sector (Deutsche Bahn, Milsped, DTS, M&M Militzer&Münch Serbia, Logistar doo, Delta Transportni Sistem) from at least two countries not available in the consortium, to offer solutions, and will seek collaboration with at least one technical EU-funded project (e.g., URBANE, IIMEO) and create synergies with innovation ecosystems. This is naturally planned to start only when the solutions, or at least the specifications or prototypes, reach advanced development stage.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport and logistics companies • Infrastructure Managers • Government agencies • Local authorities
<p>Digital channel - the Project website</p>	<p>The primary asset for promoting the Project activities and results to all target audiences, as described in Section 5.1.2 above.</p>	<p>First version ready by Month 2 of the Project, and will be updated and maintained regularly, targeting to reach 100 unique visitors per month.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types
<p>Digital channel - social media platforms</p>	<p>Most frequent and dynamic mass communication and interaction, and the rest relevant noted under Section 5.1.3 above.</p>	<p>Project presence established and being maintained on three well-known social media channels, focusing on X and LinkedIn, posting daily content and generating leads, targeting to achieve online traction of 400+ followers and 50+ monthly impressions. Premium services of the platforms will be considered to amplify the Project awareness.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types
<p>Digital channel - newsletters</p>	<p>Newsletters broadcast main activities and opportunities in a given period and anticipate planned actions for the upcoming Project stages in a systematized way to focused target subscribers.</p>	<p>SPATRA will contribute to four benchmark newsletters during the course of the Project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types

Digital channel - press release	Presents the Project ambition, objectives, and the consortium partners and their capabilities.	A joint press release will be prepared within the first month of the Project. Additionally benefiting would be the corporate press releases published by some consortium partners as part of their individual communication strategies, reaching out to their networks of customers and partners.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types
Branding - logo and templates	SPATRA is intended to remain a brand that will be used, refined and protected throughout the Project.	Logo and initial key templates created by M3 of the Project, and more are being developed, as detailed in Section 5.1.1 above.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types
Promotional material - printed	The predominant elements for events and meetings participation or organization, and a creative measure to attract a broader audience.	Brochures, flyers, roll-ups or posters, and other resources, per templates and prototypes presented in Section 5.1.1 above, foreseen to be distributed in over 1500 hard-copy items , and the use of appealing and re-usable merchandising (memory sticks, key rings, shirts, stickers) also to be explored.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types
Promotional material - slide decks	Mainly for events, e-mail campaigns and one-to-one meetings.	Several versions to be produced with the content fine-tuned for the target audience and Project achievements, based on templates and the initial version presented in Section 5.1.1 above.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport and logistics companies • Infrastructure Managers • Government agencies • Local authorities • Solution providers
Promotional material - banners and infographics	Eye-catching elements to quickly draw attention about the Project, its objectives, announcements, partners, or the beneficiaries from the funding instruments.	The Project will design and produce over 20 graphic elements of these types, integrating them in the website, social media posts, newsletters and eventually other channels. Initial results produced by now presented in Section 5.1.1 above.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholder types

6 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MONITORING, KPIS AND PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

The methods and procedures employed for monitoring, tracking and assessing the effectiveness and performance of the dissemination and communication channels and efforts in achieving their goals are outlined in this chapter. Some examples of the main performance assessment instrument - the KPIS - have been provided in the plan Tables Table 1 and Table 2 in the relevant sections above, and the complete summary list is given in the Table 4 below.

Main instrument for tracking and monitoring the D&C activities is a shared spreadsheet file accessible to all partners, where they report in standard documented form all their performed communication and dissemination efforts and generated results throughout the project duration. The consortium has decided to use the official project reporting template document from EUSPA for this monitoring of the Project dissemination and communication, to streamline the level on information and provide report aligned with the report template requested as convenient by the funding authority. This report template (Table 3 below) is organized around the common KPI and activity types as categorized and used by EUSPA for unified and comparable tracking across multiple projects, and includes press mentions, contributions to specialised journals, presentations at events, references from relevant target groups in various public documents, and all other activities, established channels and devised tools specified in the plans and descriptions in Chapters 4 and 5 above, as well as the "Other" category. It is being regularly updated by all the consortium partners throughout the project to ensure accurate and complete tracking and monitoring as inputs for assessment whether the individual and joint dissemination and communication targets are being achieved.

Table 3. The standardized unified shared spreadsheet template document for reporting and tracking dissemination and communication efforts and results by all partners

Please fulfill the data related to results of the project following the predefined KPIS types*.						
Project KPIS						
Project acronym	Date	Type*	Short Description	Link	Comment by reviewer	Comment by EUSPA
SPATRA	1/31/2023	Social media	Project LinkedIn account set-up. LinkedIn post about project Kick-off meeting	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7158390700332462080/		
SPATRA	2/20/2024	Social media	LinkedIn post about the project start at the LinkedIn page of OHB-DS	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7165699362252152832		
SPATRA	3/19/2024	Website article	Article on the website of partner NELT	https://www.nelt.com/rospatika/projekat-spatra-nelt-u-saradnji-sa-evropskom-svemirskom-agencijom/		
SPATRA	3/19/2024	Other	Article in the online magazine "MEHATRONIKA" about the project and participation of NELT in the project	https://magazinmehatronika.com/projekat-spatra-unapredjenje-drumskoq-transporta-koriscenjem-evropskih-satelitskih-tehnologija/		
SPATRA	3/8/2024	Social media	SPATRA Happy Women's day	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171802898895388672		
SPATRA						
SPATRA						
SPATRA						

The list of the defined KPIS for assessing dissemination and communication effectiveness and performance in the Project by now is not exhaustive, and additional KPIS for relevant activity or channel types of crucial or increasing interest may be introduced in the next upcoming periods during the *Interaction* and *Learning & Optimisation* phases of the strategy. Some of the relevant KPIS, additional to the fully quantifiable ones in the rightmost column of the table below, are qualitative, included in the middle descriptive column, pertaining to the generation or enablement of a specific D&E tool or its features.

Table 4. KPIs initially set out for the dissemination and communication effectiveness assessment

Activity/Channel/Tool	Short description	Performance indicators
E-mail campaigns	Broadcasting messages effectively promotes activities and results, in a manner tailored to the specific stakeholder target groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reach 500 contact points
One-to-one meetings	Engaging relevant individuals, targeting primarily logistics and infrastructure managers for outreach and business opportunities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings with at least 5 companies from logistics/transport sectors, from at least two countries not represented in the consortium. • Established collaboration with at least one technical EU-funded project and created synergies with innovation ecosystems.
Project website	Project information, news, blog, SEO, Social media integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 unique website visitors per month
Social media	Online presence on Twitter and LinkedIn (and Instagram), posting daily and spreading out news and results to wider audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 400+ followers, 50+monthly impressions
Newsletters	Publishing a regular newsletter to reach out to end users and stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 newsletters during the Project
Press releases	A joint press release will be prepared in M1 to present the project's ambition and partners.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 press release in Month one of the Project
Printing/Merchandising	Flyers, brochures, etc. to streamline the transfer of technical knowledge to target groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1,500+ hard copy items distributed • use of appealing and reusable merchandising (stickers, T-shirts...)
Slide decks	Slide decks will serve as alternative "Point of Market Entry" for the Project in events, e-mail campaigns, and meetings. Multiple versions based on templates will be produced to tailor content for the audience and update achievements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce several versions of slide decks, mainly for rail and road transport and logistics companies

Banners & infographics	Designed graphic elements and insignia integrated into the website, social media posts, newsletters, and other channels to draw attention.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20+ graphic elements during the Project
Logo & templates	A brand established and maintained throughout the project, ensuring consistency and protection.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt recognizable visual identity
Project documentation	Material detailing technical outputs, APIs, architectures, models, recommendations, promotional activities, and insights from the consortium will be accessible as deliverables on the project website and a public repository.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverables available on the project website and a public cloud repository
Peer-reviewed publications	Sharing technical achievements and experimental findings with the research and development communities through peer-reviewed publications and conference presentations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One peer-reviewed scientific/technical article in a journal • Two peer-reviewed papers in conferences
Non-scientific publications	Articles, blog posts, position papers and any other non-scientific publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20+ publications
Open Access to research	Presence on a well-known and widely used online cloud repository to manage and publish material with different access permissions, including peer-reviewed publications, shareable scientific research data, and other types of resources generated, providing FAIR data and results with open-source code and algorithms whenever applicable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 500+ downloads on Zenodo • Additional presence and publication on Open Research Europe also encouraged

Webinars	SPATRA ZENE/ZENRS will (co-)host two webinars to share technical and socio-economic knowledge with ~50 participants, subsequently recording, editing, and publishing the performed sessions as educational resources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Co-)Organization of 2 webinars
Conferences /Congresses /Fairs	Participating in conferences and trade fairs enables most intense and direct interaction with stakeholders. The consortium will showcase project results at minimally 3 events, focusing on edge continuum and industrial applications.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attending at least 3 events
Working groups and thematic expertise communities	Utilizing consortium participation in groups like OGC Working Groups (ZENRS), SPATRA intends to extend standards like OGC City Geography Markup Language. It contributes to initiatives like the Transport Community, integrating Western Balkans' transport markets into the EU.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in working groups, such as OGC Working Groups (ZENRS) or Transport Community

6.1 Assurance of Quality of the Dissemination Results

This specific procedural assurance aspect and practical qualitative metric for dissemination, primarily pertaining to the peer-reviewed and other authored publications of the project partners in scope, has been formally regulated, by the Project Coordinator (PC) and among the partners, with the relevant agreed provisions in the CA, governing the dissemination of the results by one or several partners, including but not restricted to publications and presentations, during the project lifetime and for a period of 1 year after the end of the project.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other partners at least 15 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the CA in writing to the PC and to the partner or partners proposing the dissemination within 5 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

Besides the intended publication, the paper/article, or the link to it will be published on the SPATRA Project official website, as soon as a link or document in a publishable format (.pdf, .xps) is available. All publications or any other dissemination relating to foreground that was generated with the assistance of financial support from the EUSPA will include the typified disclaimer statement from the GA Art. 17.3, stating that the expressed views and opinions in the publication are of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EUSPA as the granting authority, waiving the responsibility of the Union and EUSPA.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

D5.1 presents detailed comprehensive dissemination and communication strategy and plans aimed at effectively sharing SPATRA project outcomes, ambitions and concepts with target stakeholder groups, fostering awareness, engagement, and inspiring action. The plans encompass a wide range of various methods, tools and procedures for disseminating results, including the SPATRA website, guidelines, training materials, flyers and brochures, peer-reviewed publications, position statements, non-scientific publications, webinars, conferences, workshops, newsletters, email campaigns, and open-access research repositories, and more.

The presented developments are all founded on the solid methodological approach optimally corresponding to the objectives of WP5 and the overall project, presented in the initial chapters of this document along with the initial prerequisite performed process of identification and segmentation of target stakeholder groups and types, and the supporting engagement of external experts from diverse backgrounds to enhance involvement with the Project.

The communication plan also involves significant level of interactive stakeholder engagement and networking activities, like the creation and execution of campaigns to promote the Project and its outcomes to the target audience, and leveraging existing ecosystems to facilitate communication activities. This deliverable also reports and describes the achievement of the related significant Project Milestone MS9 - initiation of the Project dissemination and communication activities and its online presence, preceded by the establishment of key necessary communication channels and tools by Month 3 of the project. The SPATRA website serves as a central such tool and hub for disseminating Project information and enhancing Project visibility, as well as for communication and engaging target groups, supported by utilizing social media platforms such as LinkedIn and X(Twitter) for researchers and developers to connect with peers, exchange ideas, and disseminate their findings.

The dissemination and communication plans are dynamic documents that will likely undergo continuous updates to align with the project's progress, adapting as necessary to enhance and broaden the Project's outreach to target groups and effectively communicate the vision of SPATRA. The progress, effectiveness and performance of the execution of the plans will also be continuously tracked and monitored utilizing the framework of broader standardized tools and procedures presented in the previous chapter, and the obtained feedback and lessons learned optimally used to iteratively improve and adapt the execution, or the plans themselves. The relevant KPIs pertaining to the D&E achievements and generated results in the initial trimester of the Project reported in this deliverable, have been met without deviations. Most of the reported generated results, including the plans and strategy themselves, serve also as inputs for optimal tracking of the evolution of scientific and technological outcomes of the Project, and thereby for the additional development of the SPATRA exploitation strategy and plans that are to follow in the next iteration and the upcoming WP5 deliverable D5.2.